

D6.4

Recommendation for Publishers for Handling Research Supporting Data

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Abstract	The purpose of this report is to provide guidance to (Diamond) Open Access publishers for handling research supporting data. It focuses on handling research data as an important part of the published research result that should be interconnected with text publications, uniquely and persistently identified, assigned clear and permissive licence and stored in trustworthy repository for reuse. When handling research data, FAIR principles should be followed in general by the publication authors and publisher should insist on proper handling of accompanying research data.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CC	Creative Commons
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
CDS	Strasbourg astronomical Data Centre
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DAP	Data Availability Policy
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DAS	Data Availability Statement
DC	Dublin Core
DCC	Digital Curation Centre
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DUA	Data Use Agreements
EDCH	European Discovery Hub
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud

ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAQs	Frequently Asked Questions
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ID	Identifier
IGSN	International Generic Sample Number
IRB	Institutional Review Board
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
OA	Open Access
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OJS	Open Journal Systems
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PDB	Protein Data Bank

PID	Persistent Identifier
PKP	Public Knowledge Project
RDA	Research Data Alliance
ROR	Research Organization Registry
RRID	Research Resource Identifiers
URL	Uniform Resource Locators

Table of Content

1	Executive Summary	9
2	Introduction	10
3	Value of Research Data.....	11
3.1	Key Benefits of Sharing Research Data	11
3.2	Persistent Challenges and Gaps	12
4	FAIR Principles	14
5	Persistent Identification	16
6	Licensing	17
7	Repositories	18
8	Data Availability Policies.....	20
8.1	Data Availability Statements Examples.....	21
9	Ethical and Disciplinary Issues	24
10	Implementation Guidance	25
11	Tools and Resources	27
12	Conclusions	29
13	References	30
13.1	List of References	30
13.2	List of Websites.....	36
14	List of Figures	39
15	List of Tables	40

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Diamond Open Access (OA) publishers in the European Union (EU) are strongly encouraged to adopt formal guidelines and practices for handling the data underlying scholarly publications. Open science policies (e.g. Horizon Europe, European Open Science Cloud [EOSC]) increasingly recognize that research data are valuable outputs: they enable reproducibility, verifiability of science, increase citations, and drive innovation. Equally, EU initiatives like EOSC aim to create “a web of FAIR data and services” by mobilizing machine-actionable research data. To align with these goals, publishers should implement data policies ensuring that when an article is published, its supporting data are findable, citable and, where appropriate, open. This guideline report provides comprehensive recommendations — grounded in the FAIR principles, OpenAIRE/EOSC standards, and the Research Data Alliance (RDA) data policy framework — for Diamond OA publishers to manage research data. It covers the value of data, FAIR principles, persistent identifiers, licensing, repositories, data availability policies, ethical and disciplinary issues, implementation guidance, and tools, using examples from life sciences, social sciences, humanities, and engineering.

2 INTRODUCTION

Ensuring access to underlying research data supports transparency and trust in published results. Many funders and journals now mandate or encourage data sharing. European Open Science Clouds (EOSC) vision is to provide “an open and trusted multi-disciplinary environment” where researchers can publish, find and reuse data.¹ The European Unions (EU) FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data mandates and initiatives (e.g. OpenAIRE, Horizon Europe) similarly emphasize that data should be “**as open as possible, as closed as necessary**”. Publishers can facilitate this by encouraging and supporting authors in linking data and software to their publications, assigning persistent identifiers (PID), and promoting the inclusion of Data Availability Statements (DAS; see Section [7.1 Data Availability Statements Examples](#)).² In practice, this means:

- embedding data policy requirements in author guidelines;
- ensuring data and software referenced in DAS are deposited in appropriate repositories; and that
- each dataset has a PID (e.g. Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) so that it can be cited like a publication³ (following recommended citation principles⁴).

Publishers can start by **adopting a standard data policy framework** (e.g. from RDA⁵ or EDCH Guidelines⁶) and tailoring it to their scope (see Section [9 Implementation Guidance](#)). For example, European Discovery Hub (EDCH) Guidelines provides model policy wording encouraging authors to share “data needed to confirm results... under the principle ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’”. This report translates such policy language into practical guidance for publishers.

¹ [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\) - Research and innovation](#)

² [Research data sharing policy | Resources](#)

³ [Developing a Research Data Policy Framework for All Journals and Publishers](#)

⁴ [Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles – FORCE11](#)

⁵ [RDA | Recommendations & Outputs](#)

⁶ [Diamond OA policies | Resources](#)

3 VALUE OF RESEARCH DATA

Research data are **increasingly recognized as valuable outputs**. They are no longer a secondary appendage to scholarly publications — they are increasingly recognized as “**first-class citizens**”. The shift toward open science is reframing data from being a support to text into being part of the *scholarly record* itself.⁷ There are even dedicated data journals publishing papers solely describing dataset⁸, but we are referring to “normal” journals in this report. Open data accelerate discovery and reduce duplication: Grace Baynes (Springer Nature) notes that Europe’s new open-data mandates reflect that the financial and scientific value of data are finally being recognized. Open data improve reproducibility: the inability to access data has contributed to irreproducible results (e.g. only 2 of 18 Nature Genetics studies could be fully reproduced).⁹ Sharing data also benefits researchers directly: data-sharing increases citations, collaborations, and reuse. For example, Springer Nature found 63% of surveyed researchers share data, often motivated by increased visibility and credit. However, gaps remain – only ~50–64% of research data are openly available. Many researchers also report they do not receive sufficient credit for sharing data.¹⁰

This reconceptualization is driven by multiple forces:

3.1 Key Benefits of Sharing Research Data

1. **Transparency, reproducibility, and trust**

Publishing data independently (not merely “available on request”) bolsters the credibility of research. The Open Access Network¹¹ primer emphasizes that publishing data enhances *reproducibility, transparency, and re-analysis* of results, and enables merging datasets for new insights. When data remain hidden, studies cannot be reliably replicated, undermining confidence in scholarship.

2. **Efficiency: reducing duplication and enabling new combinations**

Open data help avoid duplicated effort: researchers can reuse existing datasets rather than recollect data. Moreover, combining datasets enables research at scales and across domains not possible from single experiments. This catalyzes novel discoveries and accelerates knowledge growth.

3. **Discovery, reuse, and interoperability**

Shared data become more discoverable especially when linked via FAIR principles (see Section [3 FAIR Principles](#)). OpenAIRE plays a central role in the EOSC architecture by aggregating and harmonizing metadata across thousands of data sources, thereby enhancing discoverability and interoperability across disciplines and

⁷ [Open Access to Data](#)

⁸ [Data Papers - an ode to data - TIB-Blog](#)

⁹ [The Approaching Horizon of Research Data in Europe and Beyond | For Researchers | Springer Nature](#)

¹⁰ [The State of Open Data 2018: global attitudes towards open data | Open science | Springer Nature](#)

¹¹ [Open Access to Data](#)

borders.¹² In the OpenAIRE Graph, “research data” are connected with publications, software, and institutional entities, creating a semantic web of scholarly outputs.¹³

4. **Credit, recognition, and incentives**

When datasets are deposited in repositories with PIDs (e.g. DOIs) and properly cited, they become traceable scholarly contributions. Open Access Network underscores that data publication enhances the *scientific reputation of authors* because data become citable items.

5. **Alignment with policy and funding mandates**

In Europe, open data mandates have evolved from voluntary pilot programs in Horizon 2020 to mandatory principles in Horizon Europe. The EU now expects both publications and research data to be openly shared under FAIR principles wherever feasible (“as open as possible, as closed as necessary”). EOSC’s goal is to provide a federated, FAIR-enabled infrastructure for researchers to publish, find, and reuse research objects across disciplines.¹⁴ Publishers in Europe must align with these frameworks.

3.2 Persistent Challenges and Gaps

Despite the compelling benefits, obstacles remain:

- **Partial adoption:** Many researchers still do not share data, or share only selectively. The “gift culture” in science (i.e. giving data without receiving credit) persists.
- **Inadequate incentives:** Some researchers feel they receive insufficient recognition for investing time in data cleaning, annotation, and deposition.
- **Technical and infrastructural barriers:** The cost, storage, metadata curation, and repository selection pose real burdens.
- **Disciplinary and legal constraints:** Sensitive human data, proprietary restrictions, and intellectual property issues may preclude full openness in some domains. (See Section [8 Ethical and Disciplinary Issues](#)).

Key takeaways: Given this landscape, Diamond Open Access (OA) publishers have an opportunity—and perhaps a responsibility—to **champion best practices in data publishing**. To do so, publishers should:

- **Raise awareness among authors** about the benefits of data sharing — not just for science, but for their own visibility and credit.
- **Ensure data are recognized as outputs** by requiring that data be cited formally (with DOIs) in the publication’s reference list.
- **Facilitate the process** by offering clear guidance, validated repository lists, and metadata templates — so authors are not discouraged by complexity.
- **Monitor and promote adoption** by tracking how many articles include open data and analyzing usage or citation of datasets.

¹² [OpenAIRE and EOSC](#)

¹³ [What do we mean by “Research Data” in the OpenAIRE Graph?](#)

¹⁴ [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\) - Research and innovation](#)

- **Advocate for infrastructure support** at institutional and community levels, acknowledging that data publication requires resources.

By emphasizing data as scholarly assets in their own right — and embedding policies and practices that support their publication — Diamond OA publishers help ensure that their journals do not just host articles, but help build a **connected ecosystem of knowledge**. Publishers should highlight these benefits to authors and credit datasets through citations, addressing the “gift culture” in data sharing.

- *Example (Life Sciences)*: A genomics paper depositing sequencing data in a public repository (e.g. National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) GEO¹⁵) can be fully re-analyzed by others, increasing citations.
- *Example (Social Sciences)*: Sharing survey data (e.g. via ICPSR¹⁶) enables policy researchers to test new models.
- *Example (Humanities)*: Making digitized manuscripts or transcripts available (with proper rights, e.g. via institutional platform like Digitalia MUNI ARTS¹⁷) can spark new textual analyses.
- *Example (Engineering)*: Publishing code and design files (e.g. on GitHub/Zenodo¹⁸) allows reproducibility of engineering experiments and design.

By embedding data-sharing into the publication process, publishers help ensure the **added value** of research data is realized. Actively encouraging and supporting data sharing strengthens the integrity and transparency of the scholarly record, making publications more trustworthy and impactful. It also enhances the visibility and reputation of both journals and authors, as openly shared data attract more citations, downloads, and collaborations. Moreover, by facilitating proper data citation and linking, publishers contribute to a more connected and efficient research ecosystem where knowledge can be verified, reused, and built upon. In doing so, they not only support compliance with funder and institutional mandates but also demonstrate leadership in advancing open and responsible research practices.

¹⁵ [Home - GEO - NCBI](#)

¹⁶ [ICPSR](#)

¹⁷ [Digitalia MUNI ARTS](#)

¹⁸ [Archive a release from GitHub | Zenodo](#)

4 FAIR PRINCIPLES

Data policies should explicitly promote the **FAIR principles**.¹⁹ FAIRness enhances the value of data: e.g., datasets with rich metadata and PIDs are more likely to be found and cited. In essence, FAIR data are (ideally) machine-actionable and well-described. Figure 1 illustrates the scope of FAIRness.

Figure 1: Nested relationship of data findability and reusability. All scholarly publications contain some (raw) data, but only a subset of data are sufficiently curated for reuse, and an even smaller subset are made findable with rich metadata and identifiers (blue circles). Publishing under FAIR guidelines²⁰ aims to maximize the inner (dark blue) Findable portion.

Publishers should encourage authors to make data FAIR with these particular steps:

- **Findability:** Assign a PID (e.g. DOI) to each dataset so it can be unambiguously referenced.²¹ Provide rich metadata (e.g. title, authors, abstract, keywords) so datasets appear in search/discovery tools (like OpenAIRE Research Graph²² findable

¹⁹ [FAIR Principles](#)

²⁰ [How to make your data FAIR](#)

²¹ [DataCite and ORCID](#)

²² [OpenAIRE Graph](#)

through OpenAIRE Explore²³). Store datasets in repositories indexed in registry services (e.g. OpenAIRE²⁴, re3data²⁵) to boost discoverability.

- **Accessibility:** Use OA repositories or portals. Even if data are under access restrictions, metadata should remain openly available. Data hosting platforms should support standard access protocols (Hypertext Transfer Protocol [HTTP], Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting [OAI-PMH]).²⁶ Where sensitive data cannot be fully open, publishers should require a DAS explaining access conditions (see Section [7 Data Availability Policies](#) below).
- **Interoperability:** Store data in standard, non-proprietary formats (e.g. Comma-Separated Values [CSV], Network Common Data Form [NetCDF], JavaScript Object Notation [JSON]). Use community vocabularies and ontologies for metadata and variables (e.g. Dublin Core (DC), DataCite Schema, domain-specific standards).²⁷ This often involves depositing data in repositories that enforce metadata standards. If the manuscript uses specialized data formats or terminology, require authors to document these.
- **Reusability:** Encourage or require open licenses (see Section [5 Licensing](#) below) and ensure metadata include provenance and methodology. Authors should supply documentation (e.g. README files) describing data collection and processing, enabling others to reuse. For example, publishers can require authors to detail instruments and software used in data processing.

Key takeaways: By following FAIR guidelines, the data shared through articles become much more valuable. Publishers should convey these principles clearly in data policies, emphasizing that FAIR data may be open or closed (FAIR does not strictly mean “open”). Accreditation of repositories (e.g. CoreTrustSeal²⁸) can signal compliance with FAIR-aligned best practices.

²³ [OpenAIRE EXPLORE](#)

²⁴ [OpenAIRE PROVIDE](#)

²⁵ [Re3data.org](#)

²⁶ [OpenAIRE Guidelines](#)

²⁷ [FAIRsharing: standards, databases, repositories and policies](#)

²⁸ [CoreTrustSeal](#)

5 PERSISTENT IDENTIFICATION

PIDs are crucial to make data and related entities unambiguously citable and linked. Publishers should encourage or require the authors to use the established PID systems:

- **DOIs for datasets:** Publication authors should use DataCite or equivalent to mint DOIs for publication-related data in recognized repositories. A DOI ensures that each dataset has a permanent link, just like a journal article. Many repositories, like Zenodo²⁹, Dryad³⁰, institutional archives, mint DOIs automatically.
- **Open Researcher and Contributor (ORCID) iDs for authors:** Include a field for author ORCID iDs in publication metadata so contributions are properly linked to researcher profiles and encourage or require the authors to fill them not only for the publication but also for all the relevant data. DataCite and ORCID systems can be integrated so that when a DOI is assigned, it can auto-update the author's ORCID profile.
- **Other PIDs:** Where applicable, encourage or require the authors to use recognized Identifiers (IDs) for other research objects. For example, Research Organization Registry (ROR) IDs for institutions³¹, Research Resource Identifiers (RRID) for biological resources³², accession numbers (International Generic Sample Number (IGSN³³), for example) for genes/proteins, or Handle³⁴/ARK IDs³⁵ for data archives.
- **Linking data and publications:** The article's metadata should explicitly include the dataset DOI(s), and conversely the dataset landing page should cite the publication. This bidirectional linking (data ⇌ publication) boosts discoverability and tracking. For example, DataCite's metadata schema³⁶ allows linking a dataset DOI to the DOI of the related article, and vice versa.

Key takeaways: By treating data as citable objects, publishers enable proper credit and tracking. A typical model is that each "supporting dataset" is cited in the references (with a DOI) as if it were a data journal entry. Editor checklists should verify that any DOI appearing in the DAS is resolvable and points to the correct repository.

²⁹ [Zenodo](#)

³⁰ [Dryad](#)

³¹ [Research Organization Registry \(ROR\)](#)

³² [RRID Portal](#)

³³ [IGSN e.V.](#)

³⁴ [Handle.Net](#)

³⁵ [Ark IDs](#)

³⁶ [DataCite Metadata Schema](#)

6 LICENSING

A clear, open license is essential for enabling reuse of shared data. By default, datasets underlying publications should be made available under a **permissive license** (unless legal or ethical reasons dictate otherwise).³⁷ Best practices include:

- **Apply an open license:** Use Creative Commons (CC)³⁸ or similar. The European Commission advises CC0 (public domain) or CC-BY for open research data. CC0 effectively relinquishes rights, maximizing reusability, while CC-BY allows reuse with attribution. For example, Zenodo encourages CC0, Dryad uses CC0/CC-BY. Publishers should instruct authors to choose one of these licenses for open datasets.
- **Avoid restrictive licenses unnecessarily:** Licenses like CC-BY-SA or CC-NC (non-commercial) can limit reuse and are not recommended for core data. They should be used only if there is a compelling legal/ethical reason. For example, if a dataset includes third-party copyrighted content that can't be fully cleared, a share-alike license might be an interim solution.
- **License machine-actionable metadata:** Ensure that license terms are explicitly encoded in data metadata. This can be done via schema.org³⁹ or DataCite metadata (which have specific fields for license Uniform Resource Locators [URL]).
- **Document license choices:** The DAS (see Section [7 Data Availability Policies](#) below) should clearly state the license. E.g. "Data is deposited under CC0 (public domain)" or "Released under CC-BY 4.0 license" as applicable.

Key takeaways: If data cannot be opened (e.g. privacy concerns), publishers should require explanation in the statement (see Section [8 Ethical and Disciplinary Issues](#) below). But whenever possible, maximal permissive open license (e.g. CC0) should be used to promote reuse. Tools like the Digital Curation Centre (DCC) license chooser⁴⁰ or EUDAT License Selector⁴¹ can help authors pick an appropriate license.

³⁷ [Legal issues in Dealing with Research Data](#)

³⁸ [Creative Commons](#)

³⁹ [Schema.org](#)

⁴⁰ [How to License Research Data | DCC](#)

⁴¹ [License Selector | EUDAT](#)

7 REPOSITORIES

Selecting an appropriate repository is key to FAIRness and longevity. Publishers should guide authors to reputable repositories for data deposit. Here are some general recommendations:

- **Use domain-specific repositories when available:** Every discipline has recognized data archives (see Table 1 below). For example, molecular biology data go to NCBI⁴²/EMBL-EBI⁴³ archives, astronomy data to Strasbourg astronomical Data Centre (CDS⁴⁴) archive, social survey data to ICPSR⁴⁵ etc. Domain repositories often offer field-specific metadata standards and community trust.
- **Institutional or catch-all repositories:** If no disciplinary archive exists, encourage institutional repositories or trusted general repositories (e.g. Zenodo⁴⁶, Figshare⁴⁷, Dryad⁴⁸). These provide DOIs and long-term preservation. For Diamond OA publishers that do not allocate funds for data hosting, free services like Zenodo (run by European Organization for Nuclear Research [CERN]) are ideal.
- **Find repositories via registries:** Point authors to registry tools. For example, re3data.org⁴⁹ and FAIRsharing.org⁵⁰ allows searching for repositories by subject, location, or certification. The DataCite Repository Finder is another useful search tool.⁵¹
- **Check repository trustworthiness:** Prefer repositories that are certified (e.g. CoreTrustSeal) or backed by stable institutions. Verify that the repository provides PIDs (DOIs), preserves data long-term, and supports open licenses. Publishers can even maintain a *preferred repositories list*.

When listing recommended repositories, publishers should cover the range of data types.

⁴² [NCBI](#)

⁴³ [EMBL-EBI](#)

⁴⁴ [Strasbourg astronomical Data Center](#)

⁴⁵ [ICPSR](#)

⁴⁶ [Zenodo](#)

⁴⁷ [Figshare](#)

⁴⁸ [Dryad](#)

⁴⁹ [Re3data.org](#)

⁵⁰ [FAIRsharing](#)

⁵¹ [Repositories](#)

Table 1: Examples of representative data repositories for different scientific disciplines.

Discipline	Representative Repositories / Platforms (examples)
<i>Life Sciences / Biomedicine</i>	NCBI (GenBank, GEO), EMBL-EBI (European Nucleotide Archive [ENA], ArrayExpress), Dryad, Figshare, Zenodo, Protein Data Bank (PDB (protein structures)) ⁵² , etc.
<i>Social Sciences</i>	ICPSR (USA), UK Data Service ⁵³ , GESIS (Germany) ⁵⁴ , Harvard Dataverse ⁵⁵ , Figshare, Zenodo, and domain-specific (e.g. World Bank Microdata Library ⁵⁶).
<i>Humanities / Arts</i>	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) resources ⁵⁷ , Europeana (cultural heritage) ⁵⁸ , U.S. National Archives ⁵⁹ , Internet Archive ⁶⁰ , Zenodo (for humanities data), etc.
<i>Engineering / Physical Sciences</i>	Zenodo, Figshare, NASA ⁶¹ /European Space Agency (ESA ⁶²) archives, CERN OpenData ⁶³ , GitHub ⁶⁴ (for code; can archive with Zenodo), PANGAEA ⁶⁵ , etc.

Key takeaways: Publishers should **not require** authors to deposit data in their own systems. They should support authors by partnering with or recommending established repositories. For example, a trusted university- or government-run digital archive can be promoted when it aligns with the field.

⁵² [Worldwide Protein Data Bank](#)

⁵³ [UK Data Service](#)

⁵⁴ [GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences](#)

⁵⁵ [Harvard Dataverse](#)

⁵⁶ [Microdata Library](#)

⁵⁷ [Tools and Services Catalogue | DARIAH](#)

⁵⁸ [Europeana](#)

⁵⁹ [National Archives](#)

⁶⁰ [Internet Archive](#)

⁶¹ [NASA Archives](#)

⁶² [ESA - The archives, a scientific treasure trove](#)

⁶³ [CERN Open Data Portal](#)

⁶⁴ [GitHub](#)

⁶⁵ [Pangaea](#)

8 DATA AVAILABILITY POLICIES

A clear *Data Availability Policy* (DAP) is the keystone for proper data handling and data accessibility for the publication readers. DAP sets out a publisher's requirements for making the data underlying a publication accessible, including guidance on repository use, licensing, citation, and DAS. Such policies are essential for transparency, reproducibility, and alignment with European open science mandates. For publishers, implementing DAP reinforces the credibility of the publication, supports open science practices, and contributes to a more reliable and efficient research ecosystem. Publishers should develop or adapt a standard policy, specifying what data should be shared and how. Key policy elements include:

- **Scope of data:** Define what “research data” means for your journal (e.g. all data underlying results, including raw data, code, images, models). This aligns with the RDA feature “Definition of research data”. For example: *“All data necessary to reproduce the results reported in the paper, including code and large datasets, should be shared.”*
- **Expectation of sharing:** State whether data sharing is *required* or *encouraged*. Diamond OA journals can start with encouragement and move to the requirement over time.
- **Repository deposition:** Require that shared data be deposited in recognized repositories (see Section [6 Repositories](#) above). Model policy text: *“Authors may deposit relevant data in a FAIR-compliant repository (institutional, disciplinary, or general purpose). DOIs should be assigned to each dataset.”*⁶⁶ Provide links or names of preferred repositories.
- **DAS:** Instruct authors to include a DAS in each article (typically before the references). The statement must describe where/how data can be accessed (including DOIs for open data or reasons for restrictions). Springer Nature, for instance, requires a DAS in all original research articles.⁶⁷ PLOS One policy⁶⁸ is another example. Provide templates (see Section [7.1 Data Availability Statements Examples](#) below) to standardize statements.
- **Data citation:** Require that any publicly archived data be cited in the bibliography as datasets (not just in the DAS). DataCite recommends including at least Creator, Title, Repository, Year, DOI. This treats data as first-class research outputs.
- **Licensing requirement:** Require an open license for open data (see Section [5 Licensing](#) above). For example: *“Data should be deposited under an open license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) unless legally restricted”*.
- **Peer review of data (optional):** Depending on resources, consider involving reviewers in checking data (either directly or via metadata). RDA policies list “peer review of research data” as a policy feature.⁶⁹ If not mandatory, at least ask reviewers to check that the DAS and any data links are present and reasonable.
- **Compliance/verification:** Outline how the journal will enforce the policy. For instance, editorial checks at submission or revision to ensure a DAS is present and

⁶⁶ [Research data sharing policy | Resources](#)

⁶⁷ [Data Availability Statements | Publish your research | Springer Nature](#)

⁶⁸ [Data Availability | PLOS One](#)

⁶⁹ [Practice Papers | Developing a Research Data Policy Framework for All Journals and Publishers](#)

that any claimed repository links resolve to accessible data. Define consequences (e.g. refusal of publication if data is not shared without valid reason).

Importantly, the policy must also allow for **exceptions and restrictions**. Explicitly list legitimate reasons not to share data: confidentiality, privacy (General Data Protection Regulation [GDPR]), security, ongoing patent process, proprietary data, etc. EDCH Guidelines on Research Data Sharing phrased exceptions as: *“open sharing may not always be feasible: exceptions include... confidentiality, data protection (e.g. personal data), other legitimate constraints. If data are not shared, authors should make metadata available and explain access rules”*.⁷⁰ The policy should require, in all cases, that authors provide at least a justification or access pathway.

Key takeaways: By adopting a standard policy, publishers help authors know expectations and avoid confusion. For example, the RDA policy framework⁷¹ describes **six tiers** of policy (from “Encouraging Data Sharing” up to “Requires Full Data Sharing with Peer Review”). Diamond OA journals can begin at Tier 1 (encourage sharing and statement) and progress to Tier 2 or 3 (require statement and deposit) as policies and workflows develop. The key is consistency and clarity.

8.1 Data Availability Statements Examples

A critical operational element is the **DAS** in each publication. This statement tells the reader what data are available, where, and under what conditions. Many publishers now standardize the DAS. For example, Springer Nature instructs authors: *“Your data availability statement should describe how the data supporting the results reported in your paper can be accessed... If your data are in a repository, include hyperlinks and persistent identifiers (e.g. DOI)... If your data cannot be shared, explain why.”*⁷² PLOS One instructs: *“All data and related metadata underlying reported findings should be deposited in appropriate public data repositories ... Repositories may be either subject-specific repositories ... or cross-disciplinary generalist repositories ... Authors should select repositories appropriate to their field of study ... The Data Availability Statement must list the name of the repository or repositories as well as digital object identifiers (DOIs), accession numbers or codes, or other persistent identifiers for all relevant data. Authors should also provide licensing information, where available.”*⁷³

Publishers should provide author guidelines with DAS templates. For instance, the *Journal of Industrial Ecology* offers standardized text snippets for common scenarios.⁷⁴ Example statements include:

- **Open data in repository:** “The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in [Repository Name] at [DOI].”

⁷⁰ [Research data sharing policy | Resources](#)

⁷¹ [RDA Recommendations & Outputs](#)

⁷² [Data Availability Statements | Publish your research | Springer Nature](#)

⁷³ [Data Availability | PLOS One](#)

⁷⁴ [Sample Data Availability Statements | Journal of Industrial Ecology](#)

- **Data with restrictions:** “The data supporting this study’s findings are available on request from the corresponding author; they are not publicly available due to [reason].”
- **Third-party data:** “Data are available from [Provider Name] under license [License Name]; authors had permission to use them.”
- **No new data generated:** “No new data were created or analyzed in this study”

Publishers should review every manuscript to ensure a DAS is present and appropriately filled. Reviewers can help by checking that the statement is plausible (e.g. links resolve) and that any “data on request” truly have a named contact or process. Table 2 below summarizes recommended elements of a DAS and policy checklist.

Table 2: Recommended elements of a Data Availability Statement (DAS) and policy checklist.

Policy Element	Recommendation
<i>Data deposit</i>	Encourage or require deposition of all data underlying key results in FAIR repositories, give examples appropriate to your journal research area and data types.
<i>Persistent identifiers</i>	Ensure datasets have DOIs (or other standard PIDs) and that article references include these PIDs.
<i>Accessibility</i>	Data should be open unless justified; if restricted, metadata must still be public with access instructions.
<i>Licensing</i>	Recommend open licenses (CC0/CC-BY) for the data; require license info in DAS.
<i>DAS</i>	Require a clear DAS in every article, using a journal-supplied template.
<i>Metadata & documentation</i>	Require sufficient metadata and descriptive files (e.g. README) so that data are interpretable.
<i>Linking & citation</i>	Verify that dataset PIDs/URLs resolve; datasets should be cited like publications.
<i>Ethical exceptions</i>	Accept exceptions (GDPR, confidentiality) only with justification; if no data, require <i>why not</i> and alternatives.
<i>Repository guidance</i>	Provide lists or pointers to suitable

Policy Element	Recommendation
	repositories (see Table 1 above) and use tools like re3data or FAIRsharing to find them.
<i>Community-specific issues</i>	Address field norms (e.g. embargo periods in some fields, intellectual property restrictions) in supplementary guidance.
<i>Review & enforcement</i>	Train editors/reviewers to check compliance (e.g. verify DAS, license, deposit). Consider a checklist for production.

Key takeaways: Clear and consistent DAS are essential for promoting transparency, reproducibility, and trust in published research. By providing authors with templates, guidance on repositories, and PIDs, publishers can make it easier to comply with open data practices and increase the visibility, accessibility, and reuse of datasets. Editorial oversight and reviewer engagement further ensure that statements are complete, accurate, and aligned with FAIR principles and ethical requirements, supporting a more robust and reliable research ecosystem.

9 ETHICAL AND DISCIPLINARY ISSUES

Different fields and data types pose unique challenges. Publishers should ensure that their DAP accounts for ethical, legal, and cultural considerations. The following considerations are particularly important:

- **Personal or Sensitive Data (GDPR):** For research involving human subjects, adhere to ethical standards (e.g. Declaration of Helsinki⁷⁵) and data protection laws. In most EU contexts, this means obtaining informed consent for data sharing and anonymizing data wherever possible. If data cannot be fully anonymized (e.g. genomic data, social surveys), mandate pseudonymization or embargoes. Any ethical restrictions must be described in the DAS, e.g.: *“Due to participant privacy, these data are available upon request and subject to approval by the ethics committee.”* EDCH Guidelines on Research Data Sharing advises: *“Where open access is not provided... include a description of restrictions, Institutional Review Board (IRB) review, and how to apply for access”*. If data cannot be shared at all, authors should explain why, for instance: *“Due to EU GDPR restrictions, we are unable to deposit the data publicly.”*
- **Sensitive Non-Personal Data:** Some data are sensitive due to location or value (e.g. archaeological sites, endangered species, proprietary industrial data). Treat these similarly to personal data in requiring justification and controlled access.
- **Discipline-specific norms:** Recognize field differences. For example, in humanities, sharing digital surrogates of copyrighted works may be illegal; in social sciences, survey responses may require Data Use Agreements (DUA); in engineering, proprietary algorithms may need patents. Policies should instruct authors to abide by their field’s norms and relevant laws. Even when raw data are restricted, publishers should require *metadata* or summary description of data that allow verification of results.
- **Intellectual Property:** Authors must respect third-party copyrights and licenses. If figures or tables include data from another source, permission is needed for reuse. For data taken from elsewhere, authors should cite the original source and note any license terms.
- **Conflict with Publisher Licensing:** Ensure that the data sharing policy is aligned with the publication’s own licensing (for Diamond OA, often CC-BY for articles). The policy should clarify that datasets linked from the article may have a different license (e.g. CC0), which is permissible.

Key takeaways: Publishers should clearly communicate these ethical rules. Editorial staff or ethics committees should verify that any restricted data are handled appropriately and that the manuscript’s DAS explains limitations.

⁷⁵ [WMA Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Participants](#)

10 IMPLEMENTATION GUIDANCE

To put these policy recommendations into practice, publishers need operational procedures and staff training. This is how you can proceed:

1. **Adopt a model policy and customize it.** Use resources like the RDA Data Policy Guidelines⁷⁶, EDCH *Research Data Sharing Policy* model⁷⁷ or other resources⁷⁸ as a starting point. Tailor language to the journal’s needs (e.g. strictness of “encouraged vs required”). Publish the policy on the journal website and submission portal.
2. **Integrate your DAP into author guidelines.** Clearly describe data requirements in the “Instructions for Authors”. Include examples of acceptable DAS text and links to repository finders. If possible, integrate form fields in the submission system for DAS, data links, and license selection.
3. **Train your editors and reviewers.** Ensure editors understand the policy and check for compliance at submission/revision. Train peer reviewers (via guidelines) to consider the DAS and whether the shared data suffice to reproduce key results. Provide checklists or criteria (e.g. check that each figure/table’s data are accounted for).
4. **Adjust your production workflow.** In production, verify that any URLs/PIDs for data are functional and that the chosen license is clear. The publisher can automate PID checking if integrated with a repository.
5. **Provide support for authors.** Recognize that authors may lack expertise or resources. Provide links to tools (see Section [10 Tools and Resources](#) below) and offer a helpdesk or Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) for data questions. Consider partnering with a university library or research office to assist authors with data deposition and management.
6. **Monitor compliance.** Periodically audit published articles for data policy adherence. Metrics like the fraction of articles with DAS, or usage statistics (citations of data DOIs) can be tracked. Publishers might use tools like DataCite’s Event Data⁷⁹ or OpenAIRE usage stats⁸⁰ to see the impact.
7. **Iterate and improve.** Gather feedback from authors and readers. As norms evolve, update the policy (e.g. tighten your requirements, endorse new standards). Engage with initiatives like EOSC or RDA to remain aligned with community developments.

⁷⁶ [Guidelines for the implementation of scientific publishing policies of research data citation in scientific publications](#)

⁷⁷ [Research data sharing policy | Resources](#)

⁷⁸ [Guidelines for journals that wish to establish a “data policy” related to their publications - Ouvrir la Science](#)

⁷⁹ [DataCite Event Data](#)

⁸⁰ [UsageCounts](#)

Figure 2: A conceptual schema of the data policy compliance workflow.

Figure 2 illustrates a simplified workflow for editorial handling of research data: authors prepare data and DAS; on submission, editors check compliance; upon acceptance, datasets are linked and deposited; and finally, publication includes references to data.

Key takeaways: To operate appropriate handling of research data in Diamond OA publishing, publishers need operational procedures and staff training to inform authors on the requirements and recommendations, check and enforce compliance of submitted materials and monitor performance of the system. Technical tools can be used to automate parts of this workflow: for example, submission systems may validate DOIs, and ORCID integrations can automatically retrieve author IDs.

11 TOOLS AND RESOURCES

Numerous tools and services support publishers in these efforts:

- **Community guidelines:** Leverage community guidance (e.g. FORCE11 Data Citation Principles⁸¹) to inform policy. The RDA-FORCE11 *FAIRsharing* outputs offer recommendations on choosing standards and databases.⁸²
- **Repository registries:** re3data.org⁸³ and FAIRsharing.org⁸⁴ enables searching for suitable repositories by discipline or country. OpenAIRE's Research Graph is integrating metadata records to connect authors with publications, repositories, and data.⁸⁵
- **Persistent ID services:** DataCite (DOIs mainly for data) and CrossRef (DOIs mainly for publications) offer Application Programming Interface (APIs^{86, 87}) and metadata schemas^{88, 89} for registering and querying DOIs. ORCID provides identifiers for researchers;⁹⁰ enabling ORCID auto-update ensures new DOIs auto-appear on author profiles.⁹¹ ROR provides IDs for institutions.⁹²
- **Metadata tools:** The DataCite metadata schema (via DataCite Commons⁹³) ensures rich dataset descriptions. Publishers can require keywords, abstracts, and funder info in the metadata.
- **License selection:** DCC's *How to License Research Data* guide⁹⁴ and the EUDAT License Selector⁹⁵ assists authors in choosing an open license. Publishers might link to these for author support.
- **Anonymization tools:** For sensitive human data, tools like Amnesia⁹⁶ or ARX⁹⁷ can help anonymize data, ensuring GDPR compliance while making data openly publishable.
- **Citation and tracking services:** DataCite Event Data⁹⁸, Data Citation Index⁹⁹, OpenAIRE Monitor¹⁰⁰, OpenAlex¹⁰¹ or Google's Dataset Search¹⁰² can help track

⁸¹ [Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles – FORCE11](#)

⁸² [FAIRsharing: standards, databases, repositories and policies](#)

⁸³ [Re3data.org](#)

⁸⁴ [FAIRsharing](#)

⁸⁵ [OpenAIRE Graph](#)

⁸⁶ [Introduction to the DataCite REST API](#)

⁸⁷ [REST API - Crossref](#)

⁸⁸ [DataCite Metadata Schema](#)

⁸⁹ [Schema library - Crossref](#)

⁹⁰ [ORCID](#)

⁹¹ [DataCite and ORCID](#)

⁹² [Research Organization Registry \(ROR\)](#)

⁹³ [DataCite Commons](#)

⁹⁴ [How to License Research Data | DCC](#)

⁹⁵ [License Selector | EUDAT](#)

⁹⁶ [Amnesia Anonymization Tool](#)

⁹⁷ [ARX – Data Anonymization Tool](#)

⁹⁸ [DataCite Event Data](#)

⁹⁹ [Web of Science Data Citation Index | Clarivate](#)

¹⁰⁰ [OpenAIRE MONITOR](#)

¹⁰¹ [OpenAlex](#)

¹⁰² [Dataset Search](#)

dataset usage. For example, linking DOIs in references makes data citeable; publishers should ensure such citations are indexed.

- **Publishing systems tools:** CRAFT-OA project produced various tools¹⁰³ suitable for support of Diamond OA publishing, including technical extensions (plugins) for publishing systems.¹⁰⁴
- **Publishing platforms:** Some platforms (e.g. Public Knowledge Projects [PKP] Open Journal Systems [OJS]) have plugins or modules for data policies and linking.¹⁰⁵ Publishers should explore such integrations.

Key takeaways: By using these resources, Diamond OA journals with limited financial or infrastructural resources can implement robust data practices without incurring significant costs. Many tools are free and cloud-based.

¹⁰³ [Key Exploitable Results – CRAFT-OA](#)

¹⁰⁴ [OJS Diamond Plugins – CRAFT-OA](#)

¹⁰⁵ [OJS/OMP/OPS Plugin Guide and Inventory](#)

12 CONCLUSIONS

High-quality, open research in the European context increasingly requires robust data management. Diamond OA publishers, with their mission-driven ethos, are well placed to champion open data by adopting the practices recommended here. Aligning with FAIR, OpenAIRE, EOSC, and RDA principles ensures that published research is available, reproducible, credit-worthy, and maximally useful. Key steps include crafting a clear data sharing policy, providing author guidance and support, using PIDs and open licenses, and engaging with data infrastructures. By doing so, Diamond OA journals will not only meet EU open science mandates but also enhance their own scholarly value and impact. Collaboration across publishers, repositories, and funders (as in OpenAIRE/EOSC initiatives) can further amplify the benefits. Ultimately, promoting data openness “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” will strengthen the entire research ecosystem in Europe and beyond.

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14 LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Nested relationship of data findability and reusability. All scholarly publications contain some (raw) data, but only a subset of data are sufficiently curated for reuse, and an even smaller subset are made findable with rich metadata and identifiers (blue circles). Publishing under FAIR guidelines aims to maximize the inner (dark blue) Findable portion. 14

Figure 2: A conceptual schema of the data policy compliance workflow.26

15 LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Examples of representative data repositories for different scientific disciplines.19

Table 2: Recommended elements of a Data Availability Statement (DAS) and policy checklist.
.....22

